

BIPV demo-sites with novel Glass-free colored Lightweight modules

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Lightweight glass-free crystalline silicon (c-Si) PV modules with the standard and colored configuration, designed and manufactured at the EPFL in collaboration with CSEM, will be installed on two BIPV demo sites, in UK and Romania, as part of the goals of a H2020 European project, RECOGNITION [<https://re-cognition-project.eu/>]. EPFL and CSEM combined their technologies and optimized the lightweight structure, to be able to withstand environmental and mechanical stress tests (following the IEC 61215, IEC 61370 [1]), as combined sequential tests.

Being light in weight represents a great advantage especially for BIPV, VIPV and portable applications, where conventional c-Si PV modules, with the typical glass/foil configuration, report a weight of 12-14 kg/m², or glass/glass modules even $\geq 14\text{-}20$ kg/m² (depending on the glass thickness). We present LW PV structures with a weight of only $\sim 5\text{kg/m}^2$, by substituting the typical front glass, with a thin ETFE polymer sheet, the “combi-encapsulant” [2], as front sheet, and replacing the standard back sheet with a composite, Al-honeycomb core, sandwich structure (Figure 1).

Figure 1 : Schematic diagram of the LW structure proposed for this work (a); a photo of 16-cells LW module manufactured @EPFL (b).

Ensuring the reliability and long-term performance of these devices requires a careful optimization of module structure and processing methods as careful materials selection [2]. We present the upscaling phase of our LW PV modules, with main crucial stress tests results (e.g. hail test, mechanical load and fire test), showing no degradations, neither visual defects (delamination, corrosion or bending of the module). We propose a reliable, robust configuration, with ideal thermo-mechanical performances, capable to withstand severe stressed conditions. The prototype of the two installations are presented in the Figure 2a), with some LW PV colored modules selected for the BIPV installation (Figure 2b).

Figure 2 : prototype of the 2demo sites for ventilated façades installation with LW (standard and colored) glass-free c-Si PV modules (a); photo of 3 colored (0.1x1) m² LW PV modules and the respective mini modules at the bottom (b).

Our LW PV products can easily fit a wide range of industries applications, the here presented BIPV, the VIPV, or any portable and integrated PV uses.

References

- [1] IEC61215, “Terrestrial photovoltaic (PV) modules-Design qualification and type approval-Part2: Test procedures”, International Electrotechnical Commission, 2016. IEC 61730-2:2016 “Photovoltaic (PV) module safety qualification – Part 2: Requirements for testing”, International Electrotechnical Commission, 2016.
- [2] Lisco, F; Virtuani, A; Ballif, C, “A "combi-encapsulant" for enhanced performance of glass-free lightweight crystalline silicon solar PV modules”, 2021 IEEE 48th Photovoltaic Specialists Conference (PVSC).